

Welcome!

Thesis on onboarding initiatives and success factors

Onboarding Initiatives

Mentoring

Automation

**Prompt
Engineering**

**Developer
Relations**

Mentoring

Mentor to a new hire, assisting with the development environment, the system, and initial tasks. Has been shown to strongly help new developers familiarize themselves with projects, especially in high-maturity projects.

Mentorskap forts.

Success factors to implement mentoring:

- The developer should receive a task before meeting with the mentor
- Avoid information overload
- The mentor should establish clear goals and milestones
- The mentor should be specific about both positive and negative aspects during evaluations
- The mentor should assist with setting up the development environment
- The mentor should perform code reviews and provide a system overview relevant to the task
- The mentor should lead the conversation and integrate the task into the discussion
- The mentor should help in finding answers, solutions, and framing questions
- The new hire should report to the mentor on a regular basis
- The mentor should provide suggestions and improvements relevant to the new hire's current work
- Mentors should teach new hires how to use the organization's communication platforms and their established norms
- Peer mentoring/onboarding buddy

Mentoring part. 2

Debated strategies:

- Dual mentors
- Mentors should reward the efforts of new hires
- Mentors should act as role models
- Mentors should offer friendship

Automation and Pre-configured Systems

Automate the project's build process. Provide a pre-configured system for the new hire that includes development tools.

Success factors for implementing automation:

Have a container or virtual machine ready for the new hire.

Prompt Engineering

The use of GenAI during onboarding results in coding tasks being solved faster, but with lower quality.

Success factors for teaching Prompt Engineering:

- The structure of the prompt directly impacts the resulting code
A high-quality prompt should include:
 - Context
 - Project-specific adaptation
 - Relevant parts of the function signature and the expected output
 - Specific details, such as libraries the model should use or preferred design patterns

Developer Relations

Onboarding developers into a software ecosystem from the platform owner's (keystone) perspective.

Success factors for implementing Developer Relations:

- Offer well-designed tools that support developers
- Focus on individuals who are interested in specific parts of the ecosystem
- Communicate the economic opportunities of contributing to the ecosystem to the developer
- Make it natural for developers to communicate with the DevRel team and use the ecosystem's products and services
- Encourage developers to engage in relevant communities related to their projects
- Create and maintain up-to-date product documentation. Ensure information is easy to find and understand
- Developers should be part of a comprehensive developer program that supports and engages them, contributing to both the developer and the organization